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FACTORS THAT INFLUENCE PURCHASE INTENTIONS TO BUY GREEN PRODUCTS AMONG MALAYSIANS.

Group 3

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CHAPTER 1:

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Introduction

In this chapter, the researchers will focus on factors that influence purchase intentions to buy green product among Malaysia. This chapter we will discuss the background of the study, problem statement, research objectives, research questions and research framework.

1.2 Background of the study

Green goods are ecologically friendly items that have a low environmental impact. Green products, also known as environmentally friendly products, have a low environmental effect and are safe for human health, and they meet quality product requirements by employing natural components. Malaysia is one of the countries that firmly supports the notion of becoming green. Green goods have become more popular since the 1970, particularly in the 1990, as a result of environmental and societal concerns.

Green buying intention is defined as a person's likelihood and desire to choose eco-friendly items above traditional products in their purchase decisions (Nik Abdul Rashid, 2009). Green purchasing, according to Chan (2001), is a specific type of eco-friendly behaviour that customers engage in to indicate their care for the environment. Purchase intent is an important aspect in predicting customer behaviour (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975). Consumer intention has been used to predict actual behaviour (Follows & Jobber, 1999). According to Kotler and Armstrong (2001), during the assessment step, the customer ranks brands and incorporates them into the purchase intentions process. However, two variables might stand in the way of a buying choice.

Environmental challenges such as increasing sea levels, air pollution, water pollution, and climate change are affecting people all over the world. As a result, utilising green goods will assist to maintain efficient energy, less polluted water, less hazardous produce, recycle material sources, and many other environmental benefits. Green goods also provide improved indoor air quality and are devoid of chemicals, which can lessen health issues. To address this issue, this study is being performed to evaluate Malaysian consumer intentions toward purchasing green products and to establish the link between environmental attitude and social influence on customer purchase intention.

1.3 Problem Statement

The fast expansion of the global economy is invariably connected to an increase in global consumer spending. The public is always concerned about environmental degradation caused by excessive consumption and usage of natural resources by consumers. As the environment continues to deteriorate, it has become a constant source of public worry in industrialized countries. Furthermore, it wakes emerging nations to the green movement for environmental protection. (Piew,201)

One of the most difficult worldwide issues is to reconcile environmental sustainability with economic growth and welfare by divorcing environmental deterioration from economic growth and accomplishing more with less resources. Human-induced global warming and climate change have heightened public concern for environmental concerns over the previous decades (Nagaraju and Thejaswini, 2014; Hossain et al., 2016; Hossain et al., 2019). Furthermore, this drive has prompted emerging countries such as Malaysia to become more aware of green movements and environmental conservation actions.

Environmental challenges such as increasing sea levels, air pollution, water pollution, and climate change are affecting people all around the world. As a result, utilising green products will assist to maintain efficient energy, less polluted water, less hazardous produce, recycle material sources, and many other environmental benefits.

1.4 Research Questions

To full fill the stated research purpose three questions are designed in order to guide the research process:

RQ1: What is the relationship between environmental attitude and green purchase intention?

RQ2: What is the relationship between government initiative and green purchase intention?

RQ3: What is the relationship between social influence and green purchase intention?

1.5 Research Objective

RO1: To identify the relationship between environmental attitude and green purchase intention.

RO2: To examine relationship between government initiative and green purchase intention.

RO3: To analyse the relationship between social influence and green purchase intention.

1.6 Research Framework

The study's framework is based on one of the main theories that applied in the study of green purchase behavior is Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) (Baker and Ozaki, 2008; Gupta and Ogden, 2009; Kalafatis, et al., 1999). TRA was established by Fishbein and Ajzen on 1975 (Fishbein and Ajzen, 1975, p.60). TRA is used to argue that consumer's attitudes and subjective norm towards environmental issues can influence their behavior and action towards green purchase (Fishbein and Ajzen, 1975). The detected variables are used as components of the theoretical framework in this study, which includes an independent variable (IV) and a dependent variable (DV) (DV). The research construct's framework addresses the three primary aspects that contributed to Green Purchase Intention towards Malaysians consumer. Environmental attitude, government initiative, and social influence in green purchase intention are the three reasons.

Figure 1.5 Research Framework

1.7 Chapter Summary

We have studied how to create a background for the study, a problem statement, research questions, and a research objective in this chapter. In this chapter, the speaker also taught us how to locate an article that is relevant to our research.

Chapter 1 CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

The dependent variable (DV) and independent variables (IV) will be the focus of this chapter. A dependent variable is one that can be predicted, explained, and is assumed to be the central issue of the research activity in which it symbolises the problem. The variation in the DV is predicted or explained by IV. In addition, at the end of this chapter, the research's conceptual framework and hypothesis will be presented.

2.2 Theory

Malaysia is one of the countries that heavily promote the concept of going green. Green products are those that are environmentally friendly and have a low environmental impact. This research aims to determine the relationship between environmental attitude, government initiative, and social influence on consumer purchase intentions. The literature review is a journal that has been published by another researcher to be shared with another researcher who needs their research to be referenced. In other words, the literature review is a process of collecting some analysis performed by other scholars that would be used by this researcher as the secondary data and as the key sources. This chapter describes the independent variable of the research project and the dependent variable.

The Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) model and additional criteria from existing literature were altered to establish the underpinning framework for examination in this study. Consumers' views and subjective norms regarding environmental issues can influence their behaviour and activity toward green purchases, according to TRA (Fishbein and Ajzen, 1975). The support for the TRA model in predicting consumer intentions (Lee and Green, 1990) or behaviour (Mostafa, 2007; Cheah, 2009) has been extensively explored in the consumer behaviour literature. Individual motivations, such as environmental attitude, government initiative, and social influence, are among the determinants of this study. Furthermore, this study can help to improve understanding and provide important insights into Malaysian consumers' changing buying patterns. Also, with adopted and modified a

conceptual framework that graphically summarized the stated hypothesis and the relationship between the independent variables and dependent variable as well (TRA, Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975). In this study, the independent variables (IV) are environmental attitude, government initiative, and social influence, while green purchase intention is the dependent variable (DV). The independent variables and dependent variable have a relationship with the factors that influence purchase intention to buy green products among Malaysians. The findings of the study can be used as a guide for companies looking to target the Malaysian market in terms of devising marketing strategies that will encourage customers to buy green products. Furthermore, this study can help to better understand and provide important insights into Malaysian consumers' evolving buying patterns.

Chapter 2 Figure 2.2 Theory of Reasoned Action Framework

2.3 Green Purchase Intention

According to a study by Ramlogan (1997), climate change throughout the world is a magnificent picture that shows it is facing enormous harassment by humans. As a result, society begins to be concerned about environmental difficulties that are worsening by the day. Consumers' concern for environmental issues is growing in importance these days, as they know that their purchasing decisions and behaviors can have an impact on the environment. Green purchase intention is defined as a person's likelihood and readiness to prioritize environmentally friendly products above traditional products in their purchasing decisions (Nik Abdul Rashid, 2009). Green buy, according to Chan (2001), is a type of eco-friendly behavior that customers engage in to show their concern for the environment. Purchase intent is an important feature to consider when predicting consumer behavior (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975). Follows and Jobber (1999) employed consumer intention as a surrogate for actual behavior. According to Kotler and Armstrong (2001), the consumer ranks brands and forms as part of the buy intentions process during the evaluation stage. However, two things can stand in the way of a purchasing intention becoming a purchase decision. The first is other people's attitudes, and the second is unanticipated circumstance factors. For example, a consumer's purchasing intention may be influenced by factors such as predicted income, price, and product benefits (Iman & Zainuddin, 2011).

2.4 Environmental Attitude

Attitude is defined as a mental and neurological state of preparation that has a direct impact on an individual's performance. response to all items and events linked to it (Allport, 1935). Lee (2008) defined environmental attitude as an individual's value evaluation of environmental preservation that is based on cognitive abilities. evaluation of the benefit of environmental preservation According to Nik Abdul Rashid (2009), environmental attitude is defined as "a taught proclivity to respond consistently favourably or unfavourably with respect to "environment". Attitude, rather than knowledge or behaviour, is the most important predictor of customers' willingness to spend extra for environmentally friendly items (Laroche et. al., 2001). Mostafa (2007) conducted research among Egyptian consumers to examine the problem of green buy intention, and the results reveal that consumers' attitudes regarding green purchases can impact their green purchase intention and directly affect their actual green purchase behaviour.

According to the study results, environmental attitude was not a significant predictor of young consumers' purchasing behaviour in Hong Kong, ranking second worst among other categories (Lee, 2008) However, Follow and Jobber (2000) discovered that there were correlations between value, attitude, buying intention, and behaviour.

2.5 Government Initiative

Government initiative refers to the national government's initiative or the national government's backing (Diekmeyer, 2008). The government's responsibility in environmental preservation is evident. As a role model for its citizens, the government should "walk the walk" in developing and executing environmental sustainability programmes (Sinnappan, P., & Rahman, A. A., 2011) Governments should create and promote sustainable community activities to raise people's understanding of sustainability.

The Malaysian government also used social advertising to educate and raise environmental awareness and concern among the population (Haron et al., 2005). Government laws that encourage carpooling and provide incentives to green product makers in order to enhance the country's environmental sustainability are vital in assisting marketers in advertising their green product. Pavan (2010) proposed that the government should launch a campaign to raise public knowledge of eco-labels, citing research that showed the importance of awareness and education.

The credibility of eco-labels can have a considerable impact on green purchasing behaviour (Nabsiah Abdul Wahid, Elham, et al. 2011). The government's involvement, according to Punitha and Rahman (2011) and Tsen et al. (2006), is an additional indicator of environmentally conscious purchase behaviour Both researchers, however, claimed that consumers think the government should have a role.

2.6 Social Influence

Social influence involves intentional and unintentional efforts to change another person's beliefs, attitudes, or behavior. Social influence encompasses such strategies as indebtedness or reciprocity, commitment, social proof, liking and attractiveness, authority, and scarcity (Robert H. Gass, 2015). Peer pressure is the psychological pressure that each agent felt while comparing his behaviour to those of others (Cohan, 2009). It is apparent that simply providing individuals with knowledge is insufficient to foster change. a shift in behaviour, the sense of guilt caused by not performing what was asked when others were Compliant might result in a significant behavioural adjustment. Changing the environment may be the most effective approach to improve the individual mentality (Daido, 2004).

According to Kalafatis et al. (1999), social influence is whether a respondent should or should not execute an action in the opinion of a referent. Lee (2008) revealed that social influence was the most important predictor of purchase behavior among Hong Kong's young customers.

Furthermore, Kalafatis et al. (1999) contended that social influence was the most influential element in affecting United Kingdom respondents' purchase intentions toward environmentally friendly items.

2.7 Research Framework

The study's framework is based on one of the main theories that applied in the study of green purchase behavior is Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) (Baker and Ozaki, 2008; Gupta and Ogden, 2009; Kalafatis, et al., 1999). TRA was established by Fishbein and Ajzen on 1975 (Fishbein and Ajzen, 1975, p.60). TRA is used to argue that consumer's attitudes and subjective norm towards environmental issues can influence their behavior and action towards green purchase (Fishbein and Ajzen, 1975). The detected variables are used as components of the theoretical framework in this study, which includes an independent variable (IV) and a dependent variable (DV) (DV). The research construct's framework addresses the three primary aspects that contributed to Green Purchase Intention towards Malaysians consumer. Environmental attitude, government initiative, and social influence in green purchase intention are the three reasons.

Figure 2.7 Research Framework

2.8 Hypothesis Development

Hypothesis 1: Environmental Attitude

H1: There is no a significant relationship between environmental attitude and green purchase intention.

Hypothesis 2: Government Initiative

H1: There is a significant relationship between government initiative and green purchase intention.

Hypothesis 3: Social Influence

H2: There is a significant relationship between social influence and green purchase intention.

2.9 Chapter Summary

Overall, the literature review was covered in Chapter 2, and a conceptual framework was suggested. Hypotheses have emerged because of this work. The research approach employed to conduct this study will be the subject of the next chapter.

CHAPTER 3:

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

The basic strategy or procedure used to classify, select, analyses, and interpret knowledge about a topic is known as analysis methodology. This study uses survey questionnaire as a tool to examine the relationship between green purchase intention and environmental attitude, government initiative, social influence. Data will be acquired from both primary and secondary sources in order to undertake this study. This chapter will go through the methodology used in conducting this research and elaborates the research design and data collection technique used to perform this study in depth. The research design, data collection, unit of analysis, sample frame, and proposed data analysis will all be discussed in this chapter.

3.2 Research Design

Research design defined as a framework of methodologies and strategies selected by the researcher to combine numerous research components somewhat rationally in order to effectively address the research challenge and it helps researchers to focus on successful study design and topic-appropriate research methods. Research design was a blueprint used for the collection, measurement, and analysis of data, based on the research questions of the study (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). In order to start research, a good researcher should have a detailed online overview of how and how the investigation would take place in order to start a study.

A descriptive research design was adopted for this research because the research objectives include determining the degree to which environmental attitude, government initiative, social influence have relationship with green purchase intention. Descriptive statistics, a type of quantitative data analysis, is used to describe or present data in an easily accessible, quantitative form (James and Simister, 2020). The research was conducted in a cross-sectional manner. Descriptive analysis seeks to precisely and systematically define a population, condition, or phenomena. It is critical to include a section in this study that

summarizes all of the data that will be collected from Malaysia's consumer population. All of the data was analyzed in this study, including demographic information, dependent and independent variables, and reliability analyses. Questionnaires were delivered to all Malaysia respondents by Google form and shared over social media platforms such as WhatsApp, Facebook, Instagram, and Telegram in order to analyze this study.

A quantitative approach is adopted for this study with a research survey. (Jen Mei, 2012). The quantitative approach is a research methodology for measuring outcomes that will be transformed into numerical form utilizing sampling techniques, as well as defining the link between independent and dependent variables. Quantitative approaches also emphasize objective measurements and statistical, mathematical, or numerical analysis of data obtained through polls, questionnaires, and surveys, as well as the manipulation of pre-existing statistical data using computing tools. Quantitative research is concerned with gathering and generalizing numerical data from a group of people or describing a specific event. As a result, quantitative research design is a fantastic technique to finish results and confirm or refute a hypothesis.

3.2.1 Research type

The quantitative method was applied in this study. There are several types of quantitative research. It can be classified as survey research, correlational research, experimental research and causal-comparative research (Sukamolson, 2007). The quantitative approach is a research methodology for measuring outcomes that will be transformed into numerical form utilising sampling techniques, as well as defining the link between independent and dependent variables. Quantitative approaches also emphasize objective measurements and statistical, mathematical, or numerical analysis of data obtained through polls, questionnaires, and surveys, as well as the manipulation of pre-existing statistical data using computing tools. Quantitative research is concerned with gathering and generalizing numerical data from a group of people or describing a specific event.

3.2.2 Unit of Analysis

The research unit refers to the subject being analyzed in the studies (Ashvienie, 2021). Every individual was surveyed by answering questionnaire form. For this study, Malaysian citizens was targeted to be respondents for this study

3.3 Population and Sampling

The target population in this research covered only Malaysian. Simple random sampling was adopted in this research because the questionnaire survey was distributed randomly. Simple random sampling showed an unbiased random selection and representative sample (Castillo, 2009).

3.4 Data collection method

Based on data collection, for this study the data have been collected from the respondent via questionnaire that the respondents have answer. Then, all the data that have been collected was analyzed in order to get the result of this study. Data collection methods can be divided into two which is primary data and secondary data.

3.4.1 Primary Data

Primary data is a type of data obtain through questionnaire, observation, surveys studies information that researchers get from firsthand or directly to the individual (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). Primary data is usually obtained from the source where the data originates from and is the best form of analysis part. The most common method used by researchers to conduct and gather data is through questionnaires. Using questionnaires to gather data often entails asking a subject to respond to a series of written or oral questions. A questionnaire was employed in this study. In large enquiries in particular, this is the most typical form. The survey will be able to gather information from respondents on the topic selected for this report. To gather the data for this study, the questionnaire was sent to participants via Google Form. As previously noted, the survey was distributed to respondents within Malaysian society and the general public via Google Form. Social media platforms like WhatsApp, Facebook, Instagram, and Telegram were used to send the Google form.

3.4.2 Secondary Data

Secondary data are main data that have already been gathered and are easily accessible from other sources. Obtaining information, gathering data, discovering the study's facts and findings, and creating a positive impression of the research's subjects are the goals of data collection through secondary sources. The study's secondary data set includes information from books, the internet, papers, online news, and past studies. Additionally, this study employed articles as a research book to acquire information about research on counterfeiting and journal sources to uncover any online research that might be used as a guide to assist this study. Researchers can carry out research on the indicated respondents and set the study's aims and objectives thanks to the secondary data.

3.5 Proposed Data analysis

Data analysis is a systematic process of both collecting and evaluating measurable and verifiable data. It contains a statistical mechanism of assessing or analyzing quantitative data (Creswell, 2007). To analyze and summarize all the data that has been collected from the research questionnaire, 'Statistical Package for The Social Sciences' (SPSS) version 26 by International Business Machine (IBM) was used to interpret the result. SPSS software runs statistical tests include all the most widely used statistical test built-in to the software. Research questions were measured, and the hypothesis was tested using statistics. In order to evaluate the relationship between the variables in this study, correlation is used. Additionally, researchers employ the ideas of reliability and validity to evaluate the quality of their work using the reliability test. The term "reliability" refers to the consistency of a metric, and researchers will utilize the test-retest dependability method to determine reliability. It concerns a survey's precision for validity. To analyze the validity of questionnaires, the questionnaire given to 30 consumers in Malaysia as part of a pilot study the researcher is conducting. Using Cronbach's Alpha as an instrument, researchers assess the questionnaire's reliability after receiving the respondents' responses. Cronbach's Alpha is a widely used technique that provides relevant evidence; reliabilities below 0.6 are regarded as poor, those between 0.7 and 0.8 are acceptable, and reliabilities above 0.8 are good (Griethuijzen et al, 2014).

3.6 Chapter summary

Overall, in this chapter research methodology was covered. The research design used was descriptive. The quantitative method was applied in this study and a questionnaire survey was created to collect data for this study. The data that have been collected was key in into SPSS to check correlation between the variables in this study.

DATA ANALYSIS & FINDINGS

4.1 Introduction

This part is preliminary data in research. This chapter presents the findings of this study, which were obtained from the various analyses. The raw data has been collected, arranged, and processed using Statistical Package for the Social (SPSS) software. SPSS used by researchers when it comes to statistical research. This chapter begins with the profile of the respondents and is supported by demographic data. Age, gender, race, marital status, state, educational background and income were categorized as demographics of respondents. This chapter is to explain the result to evaluated using descriptive statistics for respondents (analyzing frequency, percentage, mean, mode, median, and standard deviation), reliability tests that can interpret Cronbach's alpha while data analysis such as t -test, one -way ANOVA, and simple correlations are also decisive in this regard chapter. The reliability test which is Cronbach's alpha is using for to know the validity of the questionnaire. The type of data analysis used by the researchers was Simple Correlation to ensure there was a significant difference between the mean for individual and moderate correlation to determine the strength and direction of the relationship of the two variables. The type of data analysis used by the researchers was Simple Correlation to ensure there was a significant difference between the mean for more than two groups and moderate correlation to determine the strength and direction of the relationship of the two variables.

4.2 Preliminary Data Analysis

4.2.1 Data Validation, Editing & Coding

Preliminary data analysis is to edit the data to prepare it for further analysis, describe the key features of the data, and summarize the results. This chapter discusses quantitative and qualitative approaches to achieving this objective. Data editing is the activity aimed at detecting and correcting errors (logical inconsistencies) in data. The process of checking and adjusting responses in the completed questionnaires for omissions, legibility, and consistency and readying them for coding and storage. Detects errors and omissions, corrects them when possible, and certifies that minimum data quality standards are achieved.

Data coding is the process of deriving codes from the observed data. In qualitative research the data is either obtained from observations, interviews or from questionnaires. Coding is the process of labelling and organizing your qualitative data to identify different themes and the relationships between them. Data entry is the act connected with transcribing some type of information into another medium, usually through input right into a computer program. After data coding of the respondent is being collected, it be entered into data base. Data entry that been used is Statistical Package for the Social Science (SPSS) version 26.

4.2.2 Pilot Study

This is a small-scale initial exercise in which the researcher tests the methods that the researcher plans to use for the research project. Pilot studies should be conducted for qualitative and quantitative studies. This method is to see if the questionnaire is suitable or not for research. The pilot test is done with 30 respondents, and questionnaires were distributed to them to be answered via questionnaire form that was printed out. The reliability test was conducted using SPSS software (version 26) on these sets of data. Based on the table above, the Cronbach Alpha for Green purchase intention (DV) value is 0.837, for Environmental Attitude (IV 1), Government Initiative (IV 2), Social Influence (IV 3), the Cronbach Alpha showed 0.716, 0.720, and 0.876 respectively.

VARIABLE	CRONBACH ALPHA FOR PILOT TEST (30 RESPONDENT)	NUMBER OF ITEMS
DV: Green Purchase Intention	0.837	5
IV 1: Environmental Attitude	0.716	5
IV 2: Government Initiative	0.720	5
IV 3: Social Influence	0.876	5

Table 4.1 Pilot Study

4.2.3 Descriptive Statistics of Respondents/ Firms Profile (frequencies, percentage, mean, mod, mod and media)

The first section of the questionnaire was demographics using descriptive statistics. The table below shows the descriptive statistics of 100 respondents.

Gender

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Male	54	54.0	54.0	54.0
Female	46	46.0	46.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.3 Data Analysis Gender

The figure and table above show the gender respondents who participated in this research. Respondents from male are 54 (54%), while female respondents are only 46 (46%) out of 100 respondents who answered. Based on table 1 and figure 1, male respondents showed the highest percentage compared to female respondents who were answer the questionnaire and involved in the factors that influence purchase intentions to buy green products among Malaysians.

Age
100 responses

Age

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 18 to 20	18	18.0	18.0	18.0
21 to 23	32	32.0	32.0	50.0
24 to 26	33	33.0	33.0	83.0
27 and above	17	17.0	17.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.4 Data Analysis Age

The figure and table above show the age respondents who participated in this research. For age, most respondents are from the age group of 24 - 24 years with a frequency of 33 out of 100 respondents which is 33%. From the group of 21- 23 with a frequency of 32 respondents which is 32%. For the age group of 18- 20 years, the frequency of 18 respondents is 18%. The lowest group of respondents is the group of 27 and above which is only 17 respondents (17%). This shows that young adult people are more likely to purchase green products than older people.

Race
100 responses

Race

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Malay	65	65.0	65.0	65.0
Chinese	19	19.0	19.0	84.0
Indian	16	16.0	16.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.5 Data Analysis Race

The figure and table above show the race respondents who participated in this research. Based table 5, three categories which are Malay, Chinese, and Indian . Malay respondents has the most responses to the questionnaires as there were 65 people who are equivalent to 65.0% while Chinese respondents were 19 people equal to 19.0%. The Indian respondents are comprised of 16 people equal to 16.0%.

Marital Status
100 responses

Marital Status

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Single	79	79.0	79.0	79.0
Married	21	21.0	21.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.6 Data Analysis Marital Status

The figure and table above show the marital status respondents who participated in this research. For marital status, the highest frequency was the single group which was 79 (79%). For the married group, the frequency of respondents is 21 which are 21.0%.

State
100 responses

State

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Johor	2	2.0	2.0	2.0
Kedah	7	7.0	7.0	9.0
Kelantan	7	7.0	7.0	16.0
Melaka	6	6.0	6.0	22.0
Negeri Sembilan	6	6.0	6.0	28.0
Pahang	1	1.0	1.0	29.0
Pulau Pinang	2	2.0	2.0	31.0
Perak	1	1.0	1.0	32.0
Perlis	1	1.0	1.0	33.0
Sabah	8	8.0	8.0	41.0
Sarawak	1	1.0	1.0	42.0
Selangor	53	53.0	53.0	95.0
Wilayah Persekutuan (Kuala Lumpur, Putrajaya, Labuan)	5	5.0	5.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.7 Data Analysis State

The figure and table above show the state respondents who participated in this research. Most of the respondents are from Selangor which are 53 respondents equal to 53.0%. Followed by respondents from Sabah which are 8 respondents equal to 8.0%. While the fewer respondents are from Pahang, Perak, Perlis, and Sarawak which are only 1 respondent from each state equal to 1.0%. Kedah and Kelantan have the same number of respondents which are 7 respondents from each state equal to 7.0%. Melaka and Negeri Sembilan also number of respondents which are 6 respondents (6.0%). 5 respondents (5.0%) are from the states of Kuala Lumpur, Putrajaya, and Labuan. Also, Johor and Pulau Pinang has 2 respondents (2.0%).

Educational Background
100 responses

Educational Background

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Diploma	38	38.0	38.0	38.0
Bachelor Degree	62	62.0	62.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.8 Data Analysis Educational Background

The figure and table above show the education respondents who participated in this research. Respondents from bachelor’s degree had the highest frequency which are 62 of respondents (62.0%). For diploma the respondents is only 38 (38.0%). For Postgraduate, Secondary education and below the respondents are none.

Income

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid <RM1000	45	45.0	45.0	45.0
RM1001 to RM2000	55	55.0	55.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.9 Data Analysis Income

The table above show the income level respondents who participated in this research. 55 respondents (55.0%) are respondents with income level RM1001 to RM2000. Meanwhile, for income RM1000 below the number of respondents is 45 which is 45.0%.

4.2.4 Descriptive Statistics with Variable

Green Purchase Intention (DV)

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance
I would definitely intend to buy those products that are environment friendly	100	3	5	4.70	.503	.253
I would absolutely consider buying those products that are environment friendly	100	3	5	4.58	.554	.307
I would absolutely plan to buy those products that are environmentally friendly	100	3	5	4.46	.593	.352
I would advise others to buy and use green products	100	3	5	4.51	.577	.333
In the future i will buy green products with less environment pollution	100	3	5	4.61	.567	.321
Valid N (listwise)	100					

Table 4.10 Green Purchase Intention (DV)

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.715	5

Scale Statistics

Mean	Variance	Std. Deviation	N of Items
22.86	3.657	1.912	5

The table above shows the result for Green Purchase Intention questionnaire which the highest mean is “I would definitely intend to buy those products that are environment friendly”, where the mean is 4.70 and standard deviation is 0.503. The lowest mean is “I would absolutely plan to buy those products that are environmentally friendly”, where the mean is 4.46 and standard deviation is 0.593. The result means that many respondents agree about to purchase intentions to buy green products.

Environmental Attitude (IV)

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
It is essential to promote green living in Malaysia	100	4	5	4.75	.435
I consent that more environmental protection works are needed in Malaysia	100	4	5	4.75	.435
It is very important to raise environment awareness among Malaysian	100	4	5	4.76	.429
Enviromental protection issues are none of my business	100	4	5	4.88	.327
It is unwise for Malaysian to invest a vast amount of money on promoting environmental protection	100	4	5	4.78	.416
Valid N (listwise)	100				

Table 4.11 Environmental Attitude (IV)

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.728	5

Scale Statistics

Mean	Variance	Std. Deviation	N of Items
16.60	2.020	1.421	5

The table above shows the result for Environmental Attitude questionnaire which the highest mean is “It is very important to raise environment awareness among Malaysian”, where the mean is 4.76 and standard deviation is 0.429. The lowest mean is “Environmental protection issues are none of my business”, where the mean is 1.12 and standard deviation 0.327.

Government Initiative (IV)

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
The government should encourage consumers to learn knowledge about environmental protection	100	4	5	4.74	.441
Environmental protection is the responsibility of the Malaysian government not me	100	2	5	4.64	.595
School should require all students to take course dealing with environmental and conservation problem	100	4	5	4.65	.479
The government should subsidize research on technology for recycling waste products	100	4	5	4.69	.465
Government should enforce environmental rules	100				
Valid N (listwise)					

Table 4.12 Government Initiative (IV)

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.705	5

Scale Statistics

Mean	Variance	Std. Deviation	N of Items
20.14	2.768	1.664	5

The table above shows the result for Government Initiative questionnaire which the highest mean is “The government should encourage consumers to learn knowledge about environmental protection”, where the mean is 4.74 and standard deviation is 0.441. The lowest mean is “Environmental protection is the responsibility of the Malaysian government not me”, where the mean is 1.36 and standard deviation is 0.595. The result means many Malaysian agree that Malaysian government should focus on initiative buy green products.

Social Influence (IV)

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance
If my friends purchase green products i will support them	100	3	5	4.68	.490	.240
I learn so much about environmental products from my friends	100	1	5	4.41	.780	.608
I learn so much about environmental issues from my friends	100	1	5	4.31	.813	.661
I often buy environmental products with my friends	100	1	5	4.38	.722	.521
I often share information regarding environmental products with my friends	100	1	5	4.38	.749	.561
Valid N (listwise)						

Table 4.13 Social Influence (IV)

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.809	5

Scale Statistics

Mean	Variance	Std. Deviation	N of Items
22.16	7.348	2.711	5

The table above shows the result for Social Influence questionnaire which the highest mean is “If my friends purchase green products i will support them”, where the mean is 4.68 and standard deviation .490. The lowest mean is “I learn so much about environmental issues from my friends”, where the mean is 4.31and standard deviation is 0.813.The result means social influence is easy to spread and fast is the factors that influence purchase intentions to buy green products among Malaysian.

4.2.5 Reliability Test

VARIABLE	CRONBACH ALPHA	NUMBER OF ITEMS
DV: Green Purchase Intention	0.715	5
IV 1: Environmental Attitude	0.728	5
IV 2: Government Initiative	0.705	5
IV 3: Social Influence	0.809	5

Table 4.14 Reliability Test

Cronbach’s alpha is a statistic. Cronbach’s alpha was used to measure the internal consistency or reliability of an items. Cronbach’s alpha gives us a simple way to measure whether or not a score is reliable. Cronbach’s Alpha will be measured whether it is positively or negatively related to the survey instruments. This method is most commonly used when there are multiple questions in a survey or questionnaire that form a scale and to determine whether the question is reliable.

A total of 100 questionnaire forms were distributed online using Google Forms via WhatsApp, Facebook, Twitter and Instagram to obtain reliability test results. In the questionnaire form contains demographic profile, dependent variable (DV) and part of independent variable (IV) which is an item is to identify the factors that influence purchase intentions to buy green products among Malaysians. After the respondents had answered the questionnaire and the data had been collected, the test was performed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 28. Reliability with score more 0.9 is excellent, 0.8 and above is good, 0.7 and above is acceptable, 0.6 and above questionable, less than 0.6 is poor and less than 0.5 is unacceptable. The overall statistics show that Cronbach's Alpha with dependent variable (DV) and Independent variable (IV) are 0.940.

In the total item the statistics show that the dependent variable (DV) of Cronbach Alpha which is Green Purchase Intention is 0.715 with 5 items. In independent variable 1 about

Environmental Attitude there are 5 items in total statistic. Cronbach's Alpha shows 0.728. In Independent variable 2 is about Government Initiative and there are 5 items in total statistic and the total Cronbach's Alpha for independent variable 2 is 0.705. Independent variable 3 is about Social Influence and there are 5 items. The total Cronbach's Alpha for independent variable 3 is 0.809.

4.3 Data Analysis

4.3.1 Hypotheses Testing

Relationship	Hypotheses Testing	
<i>H1</i> : There is a significant relationship between environmental attitude and green purchase intention.	H1 is not accepted	H1:weak relationship
<i>H1</i> : There is a significant relationship between government initiative and green purchase intention.	H2 is accepted	H2:moderate relationship
<i>H1</i> : There is a significant relationship between social influence and green purchase intention.	H3 is accepted	H3:strong relationship

- There is a positive relationship between environmental attitude and green purchase intention but weak relationship and not significant stated by Cohen,1988.
- There is a positive relationship between government initiative and green purchase intention with moderate relationship and significant stated by Cohen,1988.
- There is a positive relationship between social influence and green purchase intention with strong relationship and significant stated by Cohen,1988.

4.3.2 Simple Correlation

Correlations					
		MeanS C	MeanS B	MeanS D	MeanS E
MeanS	Pearson Correlation	.161	1	.406**	.644**
B	Sig. (2-tailed)	.109		.000	.000
	N	100	100	100	100

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The table 4.3.2 show that there was a positive correlation between the environmental attitude and green purchase intention $r = 0.161$, $n = 100$, $p = 0.109$. There was not statistically significant correlation between environmental attitude and green purchase intention. It was weak and no significant.

There was a positive correlation between government initiative and green purchase intention $r = 0.406$, $n = 100$, $p = 0.000$. There was statically significant correlation between government initiative and green purchase intention. It was moderate and significant.

There was a positive correlation between social influence and green purchase intention $r = 0.644$, $n = 100$, $p = 0.000$. There was statistically significant correlation between social influence and green purchase intention. It was strong and significant.

4.3.3 Multiple Regression

Multiple regression is a statistical technique that uses several explanatory variables to predict the outcome of a response variable.

4.3.3 Model Summary

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.673 ^a	.453	.436	.287

a. Predictors: (Constant), MeanSE, MeanSC, MeanSD

The table 4.3.3 show proposed model is description of the relationship between the dependent and independent variables. The adjusted R Square is 0.436, this means that 43.6% of the variation in the green purchase intentions (dependent variable) is attributes to the combined of variation in the independent variables (environmental attitude, government initiative, and social influence).

4.3.4 ANOVA

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	6.559	3	2.186	26.493	.000 ^b
	Residual	7.923	96	.083		
	Total	14.482	99			

a. Dependent Variable: MeanSB

b. Predictors: (Constant), MeanSE, MeanSC, MeanSD

The table 4.3.4 show independent variable (environmental attitude, government initiative, and social influence) which have significant relationship with green purchase intention, this indicates $F(3,96) = 26.493, p = 0.000 < 0.001$

CHAPTER 5

DISCUSSION & CONCLUSION

5.1 An Overview / Introduction

In this chapter, the main finding of the research and the discussion of the findings after conducting the research will be explained. Also, this chapter discusses about the implication of the research, that will be explaining about the benefit of the study for practitioner, knowledge, and the policy makers and academicians regarding the research topic. Also, the limitation of the research will be discussed. Lastly, we will also add our recommendation for the future research on what can be improved or made better.

5.2 Summary of the Main Findings

This study there are three research objectives first to identify the relationship between environmental attitude and green purchase intention, second to examine relationship between government initiative and green purchase intention, third to analyze the relationship between social influence and green purchase intention. First objective of this study is accepted but weak, second is accepted but moderate relationship, third also is accepted and strong relationship.

5.3 Discussion of the Main Findings

This section focuses more on the findings and discussing and presenting data based on the research objective and research questions. The data were analysed by using correlations.

Research Objective (RO)	Research Questions (RQ)	Hypothesis Statement (H)	2-Tailed Correlation	Conclusion
To identify the relationship between environmental attitude and green purchase intention	What is the relationship between environmental attitude and green purchase intention	There is no significant relationship between environmental attitude and green purchase intention	0.109	Not accepted
To examine relationship between government initiative and green purchase intention	What is the relationship between government initiative and green purchase intention	There is a significant relationship between government initiative and green purchase intention	0.000	Accepted
To analyse the relationship between social influence and green purchase intention	What is the relationship between social influence and green purchase intention	There is a significant relationship between social influence and green purchase intention.	0.000	Accepted

Table 5.3

To see independent variables, have relationship with dependent variable it can refer to the table 4.3.2 in chapter 4 First objective of this research is to identify the relationship between environmental attitude and green purchase intention. The first objective has a significant relationship between environmental attitude and green purchase intention at P value at 0.161, this is a line with previous study conducted by Lee (2008). Environmental attitude is important due to Environmental attitude is described as an individual's opinion of the importance of environmental conservation based on their cognitive evaluation of its worth.

Second objective to examine relationship between government initiative and green purchase intention and this objective has a significant relationship between government initiative and green purchase intention at P value 0.000 and this is a line with previous study conducted by Chai (2010). This is more important due to government in environmental protection is undeniable.

Third objective of this research is to analyze the relationship between social influence and green purchase intention and this objective has a significant relationship between social influence and green purchase intention at P value 0.000. To support this objective that has a significant, it is a line with previous study conducted by Daido (2004). This objective is very important due to social influence can be the top predictor of consumers purchasing behavior.

5.4 Significant Implication of the Research

5.4.1 Theoretical

Independent variables of this research are environmental attitude, government initiative and social influence this are the factors to the green purchase intention, Contribution to the theory is expand knowledge in consumers decision making, marketing or consumers behavior.

5.4.2 Practitioners

For the practitioners, this study will give consumers more knowledge on the topic of green products and factors that influence green purchase intention among Malaysians. This research will help gather point of views and opinions of the masses from data and share on what they think are the factors that influence green purchase intention. This research also will help consumers in decision making on green product.

5.4.3 Policy makers / Society

The important of this research government and community can cooperate to spread awareness the important of green product and can use social media to spread awareness about environmental products and avoiding the products that are harmful to the environment and the government should encourage consumers to learn about environmental protection and enforce environmental rules.

5.5 Limitation of the Research

Several restrictions were found because of the study procedure. The limitation just serves as a foundation for further research and does not change the importance of the findings.

5.5.1 Factors

The research of this study has only three factors, the factors are environmental attitude, government initiative and social influence. For the future researchers they should add on the factors such as eco-labels, environment knowledge, consumption reduce, decision making model and so on, so it will be not difficult to perform this assignment and expand consumers knowledge regarding green products when the future researchers add more factors.

5.5.2 Sample size

The sample size of this study has 100 respondents and due to only 100 respondents it's difficult to generalize and can affect this assignment and future researchers they should add on sample size such as 200 or 300 respondents so it will be easy to generalize.

5.5.3 Area

the respondents that answered the questionnaire are in area Selangor so there are limit information can gather and not much information can interpret, so it should recommend the future researchers to expand the area such as to whole Malaysia

5.6 Recommendation for the Future Research

The future researchers may add on the factors by doing this it will increase or expand consumers knowledge in decision making or consumers behavior also add on the sample size such as 200 or 300 respondents by doing this it will be easy to generalize and can perform their assignment. All respondents are in Selangor area so there are limit information can gather also interpret by researchers and should recommend the future researchers to expand the area such as to whole Malaysia.

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APPENDICES

Factors That Influence Intentions to Purchase Green Products Among Malaysians

Dear Respondent,

We are from the Faculty of Business and Accountancy in Universiti Selangor (UNISEL). We are studying Business Research (PQS 3143) and are now conducting research into the factors that influence intentions to purchase green products among Malaysians.

As we know, green products are those that are favorable to the environment and have a low environmental impact. Malaysia is one of the countries that aggressively supports the green philosophy. Using green products will aid in maintaining efficient energy, less polluting water, reducing harmful products, recycling material sources, and many other environmental benefits.

Based on the survey question, this questionnaire was created to examine Malaysian consumers' factors that influence intentions to purchase green products. The survey should take no more than 10 minutes to complete. The questionnaire is divided into three sections: Section A (Demographic Information), Section B (Environmental Attitude), Section C (Government Initiative), and Section D (Social Influence).

Please respond to all of the questions. Your time and thoughtful responses in completing this survey are greatly appreciated. All of your information will be kept totally private and used for academic purposes. Thank you so much for taking the time to complete this questionnaire and for your cooperation.

Please do not hesitate to contact us for further information or questions.

Nur Irdina (HP: 019-9710925/ dinabrhim@gmail.com)

Nuaimah (HP: 016- 2369367/ imahahadi@gmail.com)

Section A: Demographic

Section A consists of demographic details. Please select the appropriate response for each of the statements.

- Gender : Male Female
- Age : 18 to 21 21 to 23 24 to 26 27 to 29
 Others _____
- Race : Malay Chinese Indian Others _____
- Marital Status : Single Married
- State : Johor Kedah Kelantan Melaka
 Negeri Sembilan Pahang Pulau Pinang
 Perak Perlis Sabah Sarawak Selangor
 Wilayah Persekutuan (Kuala Lumpur, Putrajaya & Labuan)
- Educational Background: Secondary Education and Below Diploma
 Bachelor Degree Postgraduate Qualification
- Income : <RM1000 RM1001 to RM2000
 RM2001 to RM3000 RM3001 to Rm4000
 RM4001 and above

The following questions concern factors influencing Malaysian consumers intention to purchase green products. Please tick (/) next to each answer you choose. You may only choose one answer. Please rate the following questions in the following order:

Section B: Green Purchase Intention (GPI)

Scale: (1) Strongly Disagree (2) Disagree (3) Neutral (4) Agree (5) Strongly Agree

		1	2	3	4	5
1	I would definitely intend to buy those products that are environment friendly.					
2	I would absolutely consider buying those products that are environment friendly.					
3	I would absolutely plan to buy those products that are environmentally friendly.					
4	I would advise others to buy and use green products.					
5	In the future, I will buy green products with less environmental pollution.					

Section C: Environmental Attitude (EA)

Scale: (1) Strongly Disagree (2) Disagree (3) Neutral (4) Agree (5) Strongly Agree

		1	2	3	4	5
1	It is essential to promote green living in Malaysia					
2	I consent that more environmental protection works are needed in Malaysia					
3	It is very important to raise environmental awareness among Malaysian					
4	Environmental protection issues are none of my business					
5	It is unwise for Malaysian to invest a vast amount of money on promoting environmental protection					

Section D: Government Initiative (GI)

Scale: (1) Strongly Disagree (2) Disagree (3) Neutral (4) Agree (5) Strongly Agree

		1	2	3	4	5
1	The government should encourage consumers to learn knowledge about environmental protection					
2	Environmental protection is the responsibility of the Malaysian government, not me					
3	School should require all students to take course dealing with environmental and conservation problem					
4	The government should subsidize research on technology for recycling waste products					
5	Government should enforce environmental rules					

Section E: Social Influence (SI)

Scale: (1) Strongly Disagree (2) Disagree (3) Neutral (4) Agree (5) Strongly Agree

		1	2	3	4	5
1	If my friends purchase green products, I will support them					
2	I learn so much about environmental products from my friends					
3	I learn so much about environmental issues from my friends					
4	I often buy environmental products with my friends					
5	I often share information regarding environmental products with my friends					

Thank you for answering this questionnaire.